

*Unlocking the potential of
macroalgae for a thriving
European blue
bioeconomy*

2022

Data Management Plan

SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 11.2

NOFIMA

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SEAMARK DELIVERABLE 11.2: DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Abstract

The project SeaMark contains 11 work packages (WP). The WP11 is “Co-ordination, administration and IPR”. The overall goal of WP11 is to manage the project from the start-up phase to the project completion. To achieve this goal several tasks are to be done, one being to develop a data management plan (DMP). The DMP will include three requirements: 1) The collected research data should be deposited in data repository, 2) The project will have to take measures to enable third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate this research data, 3) The DMP has to be accessible for verification and reuse, and how it will be curated and preserved. Fulfilling the two last requirements is the main content of this task, and the DMP will outline the degree, means, and timing of data access for third parties. The initial DMP is to be published in M6 and updated at the end of each reporting period (M18, M36, M48).

This deliverable contains a comprehensive overview of the different data sets used within the project, a list of the repositories chosen so far, and procedures for archiving and sharing research data after the projects' lifetime. The deliverable contains a total of 47 forms.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
AAU	Aalborg University
AGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
ALG	Algaia
ALGP	ALGApplus
AU	Aarhus University
CARL	Carlsberg Group - Traitomic
SBR	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DTU	Danish Technical University
ENA	European Nucleotide Archive
ERDA	Electronic Research Data Archive
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FEXP	Fermentation Experts
HE	Horizon Europe
IA	Innovation Action
LUN	Lund University
M	Month
MAT	MATIS
NOF	Nofima
NUIG	National University of Ireland Galway
OCE	Oceanium
ORF	Ocean Rainforest
SIR	Sirputis
SJO	Sjókovin – Blue Resources
T	Metric tonnes
UCPH	University of Copenhagen
UTR	University of Utrecht
WP	Work Package
WUR	Wageningen University

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INTRODUCTION

In all projects financed by the Horizon Europe program an overall goal is to help enable reuse of research data either collected or generated throughout a project.

Over the course of a project, considerable amounts of data are generated. If these are not sufficiently archived, shared or made available for reuse later on, it results in time and effort being spent in other projects collecting similar data, as well as discourages openness.

The Horizon Europe aims to make data FAIR:

- Findable
- Accessible
- Interoperable
- Reusable

As a way of ensuring good data management, a data management plan (DMP) was developed. The European Commission has created a template for Horizon Europe projects to follow that contains the following information about the data:

- Summary of the data
- Plans to make the data FAIR
- Other research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethics
- Other issues

This template is fill up by all project's participants generating or collecting data, one per dataset.

The purpose of the DMP is to give an overview of the data produced or collected during the project with plans to make them available publicly. The goal is to list the data, to know which one can be made public, which one have to be confidential, and to upload the public ones to an open repository in order to make them publicly available. The DMP will make sure that third parties can access the research data and that the data will be collected, identified, stored, registered, and preserved.

A DMP is a living document. With the first version being due at M6 of the project, almost no data are fully generated at this point. The dataset descriptions are about data that are expected to be generated or produced during the project. As the project progresses, participants of the project will have a better overview of the data actually used and will be able to modify the information given in the first DMP during the periodic updates of the DMP due at M18 and M36. Dataset descriptions are expected to be added, certain dataset description perhaps removed and the level of information on the data in expected to increase during these updates. The last version of the DMP is due at M48, at the end of the project. This final version will contain all dataset descriptions used in the

project. At this stage all data that can be openly available will be uploaded to open repositories, and a link to access them will be present in the dataset description.

The DMP is related to all work during the project where data are generated or collected. The target audience is mainly other researchers that may have a use of the data we are generating.

The document contains tables of the datasets identified so far, repositories planned to be used to upload the data once ready and links between datasets and deliverables. The dataset descriptions themselves can be found on Zenodo.

METHODOLOGY

SeaMark is using the Horizon Europe template made by the European Commission as well as ARGOS, an online DMP tool suggested in the programme guide of Horizon Europe. To simplify the task of participants contributing to the DMP, we sent them the template to fill up and send back to us, then we entered all information from the templates to ARGOS instead of asking them to create an account on AGROS and fill it in themselves. This allows us a better overview and control over the participants dataset descriptions.

The DMP and subsequent updates being created with the support of ARGOS will be uploaded to Zenodo and have its own DOI (one per version).

When datasets are finalized, they will be uploaded to either a field related repository or in-house repository belonging to an institution. If no such repository exists, data will be uploaded to a general repository. As a general repository, Zenodo was chosen. There a SeaMark community has been created in order to regroup all datasets uploaded there in one place under the same project's Grant number (<https://zenodo.org/communities/seamark/?page=1&size=20>).

The workflow concerning the data is the following:

- Identify the data used/generated/produced during the project
- Describe the data in a dataset form, one per dataset
- Plan a suitable repository
- Work on/with the data
- Work done/contribution to the project accomplished: upload the data to the repository

In addition of information required in the HE template, we asked participants to mention the person, institution and WP responsible for the dataset as well as name which deliverables this data will be used for. With this information present it makes the cross linked between deliverables and datasets easier.

Confidential datasets

Some of the project data contains sensitive or proprietary information. In the case of such data, options such as anonymization or aggregation will be considered when participants have a better overview of the data in order to try to make them available. If not possible, the data will not be made publicly available.

Even though there is an option on Zenodo to upload datasets under closed access, closed dataset won't be uploaded due to strict confidentiality reason: "Zenodo allows users to upload files under closed access. Closed access means that zenodo.org users will not be able to access the files you uploaded. The files are however stored unencrypted and may be viewed by Zenodo operational staff under specific conditions. This means that "closed access" on Zenodo is not suitable for secret or confidential data." (Zenodo, infrastructure, <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure/>)

However, the closed datasets are described in the DMP with metadata information which contains contact information to make it possible to first know that the data exists and second to take contact with the dataset owner and ask for the possibility to access the data.

Table 2: List of the datasets present at M6

WP	Responsible	Title	Repository planned
WP1	SBR	<i>Saccharina latissima</i> crosses	Zenodo
WP1	SBR	<i>Saccharina latissima</i> phenotyping	Zenodo
WP1	SBR	<i>Saccharina latissima</i> strain collection	Zenodo
WP1	CARL	Mutant Sequence data	Zenodo
WP1	NUIG	<i>Ulva</i> phenotyping	Zenodo
WP1	NUIG	<i>Ulva</i> strain collection	Zenodo
WP2	SIR	Seaweed farming equipment drawings and calculation	Not decided yet
WP2	ORF	Mechanised seeding of <i>Saccharina latissima</i>	Confidential
WP2	ORF	Mechanized harvesting at sea for kelp growing on vertical grow lines.	Confidential
WP2	ORF	Monitoring of selected <i>Saccharina latissima</i> strains in Faroe Islands and Brittany	Confidential
WP2	ORF	Post-harvest processing into storage stable products	Confidential
WP2	ORF	Growth and site parameters in a new site in FO and NO	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Fish production data to include in software for farm management	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Monitorization of abiotic factors	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Quality control of seaweed biomass	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Ratio of biomass losses from harvest to storage	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Seaweed chemical characterization	Confidential
WP2	ALGP	Seaweed production data	Partially Zenodo
WP3	OCE	Development plan for product specification	Confidential
WP3	OCE	Biorefinery plant implementation plan	Confidential
WP3	OCE	Biorefinery processing of 450 T ww <i>S. latissima</i>	Confidential

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The first version of the DMP contains 47 forms in total. As the project will run and the DMP will be updated a track record of the changes will be kept in table 1.

Table 1: Overview of the DMP through the project's lifetime

Deliverable	Month	Number of forms	Modifications
D11.2	M6	47	
<i>Upcoming</i>			
D11.2 update	M18		
D11.3	M36		
D11.5	M48		

Table 2 gives an overview of the 47 dataset descriptions, classified by WP and to which repository they are planned to be uploaded when open.

WP3	OCE	Product analysis data	Confidential
WP3	OCE	Fucoxanthin product dossier	Zenodo
WP3	OCE	Beta-glucan product dossier	Zenodo
WP4	UCPH	<i>In vitro</i> simulated gastrointestinal digestion of feed supplement prototypes developed by AAU	ERDA at UCPH
WP4	AAU	Chemical and biological characteristics post fermentation	Zenodo
WP4	AU, FEXP, UCPH,	The health-promoting effect of fermented seaweed	ENA for sequencing, Zenodo
WP5	ALG	Co-coextraction of Ulva products.	Confidential
WP5	ALG	Alginates coextraction dataset.	Confidential
WP5	ALG	Fucoxanthins coextraction dataset.	Confidential
WP6	MAT, DTU, LUN, UTR	Alginate lyases and data on products produced by enzyme catalysis	Genbank
WP6	DTU, MAT, UTR	Enzymatic processing of fucoxanthins	Genbank
WP6	MAT, LUN, UTR	Enzymatic processing of laminarin	Genbank
WP6	LUN, MAT, UTR	Ulvan modifying enzymes and enzymatic processing of Ulvan	Genbank
WP7	NOF	Flagship products and go-to-market strategy	Confidential
WP7	NOF	Market application potential	Confidential
WP7	NOF	Recommendations for scenario testing	Confidential
WP7	NOF	Pilot scale sales	Confidential
WP7	NOF	Commercial scale sales	Confidential
WP8	SJO	Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product – business exploitation	Zenodo
WP8	SJO	Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product	Partly, Zenodo
WP8	NOF	Data for techno-economic analysis of flagship products	Partly, Zenodo
WP8	WUR	Data for value chain analysis of flagship products	Partly, Zenodo
WP8	SJO	Data for socio-economic impacts SeaMark product	Partly, Zenodo
WP9	WUR	LCA data set	Confidential
WP9	WUR	Ecosystem service data set	Zenodo

As summarized in table 3, most of the datasets that can be made public will be uploaded to Zenodo. Five datasets are planned to be uploaded to a field related repository on genetics, one to an institutional repository, and one is not decided yet. A great number of datasets are classified as confidential as they contain sensitive commercial data. This was to be expected due to the nature of the SeaMark project being an Innovation Action (IA). Most of the closed datasets come from the industry partners: Ocean Rainforest (ORF), Algaia (ALG), Oceanium (OCE) and ALGApplus (ALGP) as well as from Nofima (NOF) that is analysing the market strategies for the products of these industries.

Table 3: Repositories chosen, and the number of datasets planned to be uploaded to each

Repositories	Type of repository	Number of datasets
Zenodo	Public	16
Genbank	Field related	4
ENA	Field related	1
ERDA at UCPH	Institutional	1
Confidential		24
Not decided yet		1
SUM		47

In order to make this project as open as it can be and increase re-use of data, we decided to cross reference the datasets and the deliverables. In addition to linking the datasets to deliverables, in each deliverable is a reference to the datasets used to produce it. By doing that anyone interested in a deliverable can easily find the relevant data behind it and vice-versa. Table 4 gives an overview of the links identified so far.

Table 4: Links between datasets and deliverables

Datasets title	Deliverables
<i>Saccharina latissima</i> crosses	D1.2
<i>Saccharina latissima</i> phenotyping	D1.2, D1.4, D1.6
<i>Saccharina latissima</i> strain collection	D1.2
Mutant Sequence data	D1.7
<i>Ulva</i> phenotyping	D1.1, D1.3, D1.5
<i>Ulva</i> strain collection	D1.3
Seaweed farming equipment drawings and calculation	D2.2, D2.3, D2.4
Mechanised seeding of <i>Saccharina latissima</i>	D2.1, D2.4
Mechanized harvesting at sea for kelp growing on vertical grow lines.	D2.4
Monitoring of selected <i>Saccharina latissima</i> strains in Faroe Islands and Britany	D1.4, D1.6
Post-harvest processing into storage stable products	D2.3
Growth and site parameters in a new site in FO and NO	D2.2
Monitorization of abiotic factors	D2.6
Seaweed chemical characterization	D2.6
Seaweed production data	D1.1, D2.6
Development plan for product specification	D3.1
Biorefinery plant implementation plan	D3.2
Biorefinery processing of 450 T ww <i>S. latissima</i>	D3.3
Product analysis data	D3.4
Fucoidan product dossier	D3.5
Beta-glucan product dossier	D3.6
Chemical and biological characteristics post fermentation	D4.1, D4.3
Co-coextraction of <i>Ulva</i> products.	D5.4, D5.5, D6.7, D7.4, D8.1, D8.3, D8.6, D9.7
Alginates coextraction dataset.	D5.2, D5.3, D5.6, D7.4, D8.1, D8.3, D8.6, D9.7
Fucoidans coextraction dataset.	D5.2, D5.3, D5.6, D7.4, D8.1, D8.3, D8.6, D9.7
Alginate lyases and data on products produced by enzyme catalysis	D6.2, D6.4, D6.5
Enzymatic processing of fucoidans	D6.4, D6.5, D6.6
Enzymatic processing of laminarin	D6.3, D6.4, D6.5
Ulvan modifying enzymes and enzymatic processing of Ulvan	D6.4, D6.5, D6.7
Flagship products and go-to-market strategy	D7.1
Market application potential	D7.3
Recommendations for scenario testing	D7.4
Pilot scale sales	D7.5
Commercial scale sales	D7.6
Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product - business exploitation	D8.7
Data for characterization of supply chains of SeaMark product	D8.1
Data for techno-economic analysis of flagship products	D8.3, D8.6
Data for value chain analysis of flagship products	D8.2, D8.3
Data for socio-economic impacts SeaMark product	D8.4
LCA data set	D9.6
Ecosystem service data set	D9.2, D9.3, D9.4, D9.5

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the first version of the DMP contains 47 dataset descriptions. Half of it (24) are confidential due to commercially sensitive data. The majority of the dataset that will be open will be uploaded under the SeaMark community on Zenodo. None of the data are ready for upload yet but the dataset descriptions can be found on Zenodo.

The next DMP update will take place at M18 of the project, in other words at the end of December 2023, and is expected to contain more detailed information about the data, especially concerning the dataset summary where there are many discrepancies at this stage on the level of information provided between datasets.

DATASET

Dataset descriptions themselves can be found on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7261409>

REFERENCES

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- EU Grants AGA – Annotated Model Grant Agreement EU Funding Programmes 2021-2027 PRE-DRAFT (HE) incl. update for ALL PROGRAMMES, 30 November 2021
- ARGOS, <https://argos.openaire.eu/splash/#page-top>
- Horizon Europe, Data Management Plan template, Version 1.0, 05 May 2021
- Zenodo, infrastructure, <https://about.zenodo.org/infrastructure> (Accessed the 27 October 2022)

ANNEX

Horizon Europe DMP template

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan ('DMP') is established and regularly updated. The use of this template is recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries. In completing the sections of the template, the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17, must be addressed.

1. Data Summary

- a) Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

- b) What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- c) What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- d) What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- e) What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- f) To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- a) Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- b) Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- c) Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- d) Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

- a) Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- b) Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- c) Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- a) Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- b) If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- c) Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- d) If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- e) How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

- f) Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

2.3 Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?
- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

2.4 Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

6. Ethics

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?